

ISic0741

I.Sicily inscription 0741

Language

Latin

Type

seat

inscription

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Amphitheatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]NI[]SMV[]AR[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491631

EDCS 21900462

Bibliography

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Buonocore, M. 1992. Epigrafia anfiteatrale dell'occidente romano. III. Regiones Italiae II-V, Sicilia, Sardinia et Corsica. *Epigrafia anfiteatrale dell'occidente romano*. Rome. At 121 no.85.11, tav.XXXVII fig.3

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